

Full spectrum Solar Direct Air Capture & Conversion: Optical Design of the Solar Concentrating Unit

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1. Introduction

An important building block in the chemical industry, ethylene is used to produce numerous materials, such as plastics and detergents. It represents the largest volume organic chemical produced in the world. In this context, the EU-funded project “Full spectrum Solar Direct Air Capture & Conversion (SolDAC)” adopts a game-changing approach to transform the ethylene and by-product ethanol (C₂ products) industries into zero-carbon sectors through solar energy and air mining synergy. This project aims at demonstrating a climate-neutral and market-competitive process to upgrade such difficult-to-decarbonise sectors, having all the characteristics for partaking in the future chemical industry. The SolDAC process exploits the full spectrum of solar radiation by powering the downstream direct air capture and conversion processes with energy from a spectral-splitting hybrid photovoltaic-thermal solar collector. A low-temperature-heat-driven (<80°C) direct air capture, concentrating and pressurisation device flexibly modulates CO₂ purity related to primary solar energy availability. The DAC unit partly feeds: i) a photo-electrochemical (PEC) stack to produce ethylene and ethanol (C₂ products) and ii) a pipeline for storage to offset the carbon footprint of the process and gain carbon credits, making the whole process truly zero-carbon. Fig. 1 provides an overview of the main energy and mass flows among the units composing the integrated SolDAC direct air capture, storage and utilisation process [1]. This research focuses on the optical design of the full spectrum solar (FSS) concentrator.

2. System description

FSS concentrator is designed for an efficient use of the whole spectrum and higher combined heat and electricity generation global efficiency. The FSS consists of a linear Fresnel concentrator and a beam splitting secondary optical element (SOE)/receiver. NIR wavelengths are absorbed and conveyed by a liquid (e.g. water) to a dedicated heat storage. VIS wavelengths are collected and can be either converted into electricity by photovoltaic (PV) cells placed at the exit of the SOE or extracted by an optical guiding system. The heat produced by the liquid absorption will feed the DAC unit and the VIS fraction will be used either to reduce the electricity needs of the PEC unit or generate photovoltaic electricity.

The Fresnel concentrator designed is formed by 10 reflectors (9 cm wide by 1 m long) of parabolic shape that concentrate the incident irradiance into a line. At the focal plane, the developed spectral splitting SOEs are located. The SOEs are made up of solid and liquid elements. The liquid element not only absorbs the NIR photons but it also acts as an optical element that participates in concentrating the incident beam. In addition, the solid parts of the receiver, jointly with the liquid, ensure beam étendue-squeezing to achieve a punctual focus from the linear one produced by the Fresnel reflector.

3. Results

As indicated in the previous section, the Fresnel concentrator has been designed and the optical performance has been theoretically determined. Regarding the SOE, the optical design has been finished, and the optical performance of the element has been theoretically and experimentally assessed. A photograph of one of the SOEs fabricated for the laboratory (for experimental characterisation and optical model validation) is shown in Fig. 2a. Fig. 2b charts the spectral optical efficiency of the rays that exit the SOE with respect to those at the entrance and the absorptance of the liquid element for 0° azimuth and 50° solar elevation, for a concentrator tilt angle of 40°. The system has been assessed in Lleida (Latitude = 41.6°, Longitude = 0.622°), in Spain. Photons up to 900 nm are transmitted through the SOE, for direct PV use or to feed the PEC unit, with an optical efficiency above 80%. Photons above 1300 nm are fully absorbed by the liquid for heat generation.

References

[1] SolDAC project, <https://soldac-project.eu>

Figure 1. SolDAC process

Figure 2. a) Fabricated secondary optical element; b) Optical efficiency of the photons exiting the SOE (η) and absorptance (by the liquid filter) of the photons that are used to generate heat (A)

a)

b)

